

Biotic and isotopic vestiges of oligotrophy on continental shelves during Oceanic Anoxic Event 2**Zofia Dubicka¹, Maciej Bojanowski², Danuta Peryt³, and Marcin Barski¹**¹Faculty of Geology, University of Warsaw, Żwirki i Wigury 93, 02-089 Warsaw, Poland.²Institute of Geological Sciences, Polish Academy of Science, Twarda 51/55, 00-818 Warsaw, Poland.³Institute of Paleobiology, Polish Academy of Science, Twarda 51/55, 00-818 Warsaw, Poland.**Contents of this file**

Figures S1

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Figure S1. Selected taxa of dinoflagellate cyst occurring in studied section. Scale bars represent 50 µm. 1. *Spiniferites ramosus* (sample 13), 2. *Cribroperidinium* sp. (sample 9), 3. *Chlamyдохorella* sp. (sample 13), 4. *Cribroperidinium edwardsii* (sample 15), 5. *Cyclonephelium compactum* (sample 311), 6. *Odontochitina operculata* (sample 38), 7. *Hystrichodinium pulchrum* (sample 9), 8. *Hystrichosphaeridium tubiferum* (sample 9), 9. *Oligosphaeridium complex* (sample 15), 10. *Scriniodinium campanula* (sample 13), 11. *Wrevittia cassidata* (sample 11), 12. *Tanyosphaeridium* sp. (sample 41), 13. *Palaeohystrichophora infusorioides* (sample 13), 14. *Impagidinium* sp. (sample 7), 15. *Litosphaeridium siphoniphorum* (sample 11)

S-19 samples	$\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{VPDB}} [\text{‰}]$
4	1.69
5	1.76
6	1.61
7	1.75
8	1.91
9	1.72
10	1.79
11	1.79
12	1.93
13	2.08
14	2.20
15	2.40
16	2.48
17	2.41
18	2.71
19	2.84
20	2.78
21	3.04
22	3.03
23	3.34
24	3.52
25	3.32
26	3.34
27	3.14
28	3.25
29	3.34
30	3.18
31	3.22
32	3.11
33	3.16
34	2.94
35	3.00
36	3.26
37	3.08
39	3.16
40	3.12
41	3.18
42	3.18
43	3.20
45	3.43

46	3.29
47	3.17
48	3.51
49	3.27
50	2.77
51	2.94
52	2.74
53	2.61
54	2.51

Table S1. Carbon stable-isotope data for the upper Cenomanian – lower Turonian limestones, the S-19 borehole. Sample numbers correspond to those in Figure 1.

sample weight (grams)	32	25	89	22	37	30	110	76	69	50	62	72	85
sample	7	9	11	13	15	20	22	25	28	32	33	38	41
<i>Achomosphaera/Spiniferites</i> spp.	112	98	60	146	121	0	0	0	0	0	0	25	13
<i>Apteodinium granulatum</i>	3	5				0	0	0	0	0	0		
<i>Batiacasphaera</i> sp.	4	8	6	12	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	2
<i>Callaiosphaeridium asymmetricum</i>	1	4				0	0	0	0	0	0		
<i>Chlamydophorella</i> sp.		12			7	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	
<i>Coronifera oceanica</i>	2					0	0	0	0	0	0		
<i>Cribroperidinium edwardsii</i>	2	4				0	0	0	0	0	0		
<i>Cribroperidinium</i> sp.		12				0	0	0	0	0	0		
<i>Cyclonephelium</i> sp.	3	19	15	12	22	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	4
<i>Dinopterygium cladoides</i>	3	19	7			0	0	0	0	0	0		
<i>Florentinia mantelli</i>	3		4		2	0	0	0	0	0	0		
<i>Gonyaulacusta cassidata</i>	2	6				0	0	0	0	0	0		
<i>Heterosphaeridium difficile</i>						0	0	0	0	0	0	2	
<i>Heterosphaeridium heteracanthum</i>		6			2	0	0	0	0	0	0		1
<i>Heterosphaeridium</i> sp.		7				0	0	0	0	0	0	9	
<i>Heterosphaeridium verdierii</i>		2				0	0	0	0	0	0		
<i>Hystrichodinium pulchrum</i>	10	23	5	9		0	0	0	0	0	0		
<i>Litosphaeridium fenestreconum</i>					2	0	0	0	0	0	0		
<i>Litosphaeridium siphoniphorum</i>				5	19	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1
<i>Odontochitina</i> spp	24	31	30	63	22	0	0	0	0	0	0	26	10
<i>Oligosphaeridium complex</i>	4	18	23		10	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	
<i>Oligosphaeridium pulcherimum</i>		3			12	0	0	0	0	0	0		
<i>Operculodinium</i> sp.						0	0	0	0	0	0		1
<i>Palaeohystrichophora infusorioides</i>			0		1	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	7

<i>Pervosphaeridium</i> sp.	8	13	16		14	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	3
<i>Psaligonyaulax deflandrei</i>	5					0	0	0	0	0	0		
<i>Pterodinium/ Impagidiniium</i> spp.	21	29	10	22	17	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	2
<i>Scriniodinium campanula</i>			4			0	0	0	0	0	0	7	1
<i>Senoniasphaera rotundata</i> <i>rotundata</i>						0	0	0	0	0	0	3	1
<i>Tanyosphaeridium</i> sp.	1	2			1	0	0	0	0	0	0		2
<i>Sentusidinium</i> spp.	15	40	13	0	22	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	2
<i>Thallasiphora</i> sp.		3				0	0	0	0	0	0		
<i>Xenascus</i> sp.	11				9	0	0	0	0	0	0		

Table S2. Dinoflagellate counting data

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47			
8	33	86	97	128	0	12	12	12	10	15	0	1	1	0	2	0	3	2	2	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	32	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	470
9	12	93	152	168	28	5	6	10	2	40	0	1	0	3	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	50	2	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	581	
10	10	91	120	131	49	10	10	15	12	46	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	2	3	2	0	1	0	0	0	39	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	545	
11	12	70	171	109	20	10	10	20	16	46	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	2	2	3	0	3	0	0	0	38	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	2	0	0	0	0	541	
12	23	33	101	79	0	2	2	4	16	65	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	1	2	1	2	0	1	0	0	0	40	3	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	388		
14	0	40	70	53	10	4	6	12	3	23	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	3	4	1	0	0	0	25	4	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	4	0	0	0	0	0	272		
15	0	72	134	150	16	14	20	30	6	30	0	0	1	1	0	0	6	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	27	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	2	0	0	0	0	531	
16	0	40	156	90	6	5	8	17	0	43	0	0	1	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	24	2	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	411	
17	0	40	82	54	10	20	10	60	4	28	2	0	1	10	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	47	0	0	36	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	409
18	0	98	59	140	119	80	90	166	10	0	1	0	1	5	0	0	0	0	1	2	1	1	0	0	8	0	0	1	11	110	1	0	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	1	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	920		
19	0	33	101	72	30	28	28	50	6	15	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	0	63	0	6	23	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	476	
20	0	40	147	71	30	36	18	195	7	1	0	0	0	2	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	5	0	3	0	8	19	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	593	
21	0	8	35	28	26	16	10	91	4	1	0	2	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	72	2	0	13	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	322	
22	0	0	0	0	0	19	14	76	7	13	0	0	1	5	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	46	2	1	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	199	
24	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31	0	37	0	24	114	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	209
25																																																	0	
26	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29	0	0	27	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	57	
27	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	13	4	0	3	19	4	3	0	5	0	2	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	70
28	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	63	2	65	2	3	57	8	4	0	2	0	1	1	3	8	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	224
30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24	56	14	12	7	0	36	16	10	0	6	0	13	1	0	12	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	211
32	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21	74	19	12	5	0	11	53	9	0	6	0	10	0	0	1	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	224	
33	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	21	3	20	0	3	15	5	3	4	5	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	93	
34	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29	67	11	31	12	2	6	21	7	3	4	0	6	1	3	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	209	
35	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31	40	2	11	12	11	3	27	7	9	13	0	25	0	0	5	5	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	203	
37-38	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	19	22	4	16	5	1	6	20	0	4	4	0	4	0	4	7	0	3	4	1	0	0	4	0	128		

39-42	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	6	0	4	6	0	3	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	33	
44	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24	18	2	49	0	3	0	3	6	0	3	0	1	0	2	10	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	128
45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	20	58	0	65	19	14	0	13	10	2	24	0	0	0	1	11	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	238
47	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33	13	3	24	20	27	0	7	11	19	20	0	10	0	0	12	5	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	20	225
48	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34	21	11	23	53	1	0	13	24	13	3	0	9	0	0	11	6	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	19	244	
49	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33	21	0	45	55	1	0	14	9	4	10	0	8	1	0	11	5	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	220	
50	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	48	30	3	10	18	17	0	15	11	12	4	5	21	0	0	3	7	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	206	
51	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	46	19	9	7	13	12	0	30	25	3	11	0	28	1	0	2	2	0	1	2	11	1	0	5	228		
52	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	61	6	4	10	13	42	0	12	11	0	6	2	17	0	0	3	0	0	2	0	24	6	0	1	220		
53	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	38	31	5	7	12	0	0	48	11	1	4	0	31	0	1	5	3	1	0	1	4	20	0	4	227		
54	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	53	23	7	22	0	0	0	28	4	3	15	0	46	0	0	3	1	0	2	0	1	2	0	2	212		
55	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	50	33	9	17	11	0	0	21	10	2	1	0	42	0	1	9	5	0	0	0	3	1	0	6	221		

Table S3. Foraminiferal data.

1. *Orithostella formosa* (Brotzen)
2. *Gavelinella intermedia* (Berthelin)
3. *Gavelinella baltica* Brotzen
4. *Gavelinella cenomanica* Brotzen
5. *Gavelinella lodziensis* Gawor-Biedowa
6. *Tritaxia pyramidata* Cushman and Jarvis
7. *Tritaxia macfadyeni* Cushman + *T. plummerae* Cushman
8. *Tritaxia tricarinata* (Reuss)
9. *Eggerellina mariae* Ten Dam
10. *Gyroidinoides subconicus* (Vasilenko)
11. *Psilocitharella paucistriata* (Reuss)
12. *Dorothia* sp.
13. *Verneuilinoides gorzoviensis* Gawor-Biedowa
14. *Plectina mariae* (Franke)

15. *Pseudotextulariella cretosa* (Cushman)
16. *Ammodiscus peruvianus* Berry
17. *Tristix excavatus* (Reuss)
18. *Lagena sulcata* Brady
19. *Arenobulimina frankei* Cushman
20. *Arenobulimina advena* Cushman
21. *Marginulina* sp.
22. *Saracenaria* sp.
23. *Dentalina* spp.
24. *Gyroidinoides infracretacea* (Morozova)
25. *Valvulineria lenticula* (Reuss)
26. *Eponides karsteni* (Reuss)
27. *Lenticulina* spp.
28. *Marssonella oxycona* (Reuss)
29. *Lingulogavelinella globosa*
30. *Gavelinella belorussica* (Akimez)+ *Cibicides gorbenkoi* (Akimez)
31. *Praebulimina* sp.
32. *Cibicides polyrraphes* (Reuss)
33. *Globorotalites hangensis* Vasilenko
34. *Gavelinella vesca* (Bykova)
35. *Gavelinella* sp.
36. *Tappanina eouvigeriniformis* (Keller)
37. *Allomorphina* sp.
38. *Nodosariella* sp.
39. *Arenobulimina preslii* (Reuss)
40. *Tritaxia* sp. + *Gaudryina* sp.
41. *Planularia* sp.
42. *Ataxophragmium* sp.
43. *Globulina* sp.

44. *Gavelinella ammonoides* (Reuss)
45. *Pyramidina* sp.
46. *Cibicides/Orithostella*?
47. *Gavelinella berthelini* (Keller)